

Dark Sector Temporal and Not Spatial Displacement Interaction Observed In $H \rightarrow \mu + \mu^-$ Decay

Emmanouil Markoulakis, Department of Electronic Engineering, Computer Technology Informatics & Electronic Devices Laboratory, Hellenic Mediterranean University (HMU), Romanou 3, Chania 73133, Crete, Greece. Corresponding author E-mail: markoul@hmu.gr, ORCID: 0000-0003-0146-2621.

Abstract

We offer herein an alternative explanation and interpretation to the possibility of kinetic mixing of a Higgs Boson with the dark sector during the Higgs Boson decay to a muon pair that would be used as proof of the connection of the Higgs with the dark sector and experimentally prove the dark sector. We therefore challenge the current wide accepted hypothesis in the dark sector community and research, that this interaction would be observed in the ATLAS or CMS detector data at CERN as a spatial displacement in the origin point of the Higgs Boson appearance, different and being spatially displaced from the original beams collision point at the center of the detector. We predict that both this Higgs Boson and muon pair would still origin at the beams collision point at the center of the detector but instead of the origin point's spatial displacement a temporal displacement is happening in the Time-of-Flight (ToF) of the muon pair towards the muons detector's outer layer. This temporal displacement would be measured as an anomalous shortened ToF of the muon pair upon detection but not because the path was shortened i.e. spatial displacement of the muon pair origin, but instead possible dark-sector-muon oscillation which we predict would be indistinguishable from instantaneous quantum tunneling effect or with a superluminal speed upper bound.

Keywords: Dark Sector, Higgs Boson, muon decay, superluminal kinetic mixing, CERN

1. Introduction

The concept of spatial displacement of the origin point of $H \rightarrow \mu + \mu^-$ Decay described due to possible dark sector mixing is shown in **Fig.1** taken from a Youtube PBS channel presentation [\[1\]](#):

Figure 1. Dark Sector Kinetic Mixing hypothesis spatially displaces the origin point of the $H \rightarrow \mu^+ \mu^-$ Decay in the CERN Detectors [1].

Opposite to the above shown in **Fig.1** concept of spatial displacement the author herein predicts that the signal propagates from the original beams collision point located normally at the center of the detector and not spatially from a displaced off-center origin.

But instead, the propagation time of the measured signal thus Time-of Flight (ToF) of the muon pair particles towards the muon detector's layer will be cut short by an instantaneous propagation speed segment or possible upper bound superluminal propagation speed dark sector signal similar and possible indistinguishable from a quantum tunneling effect. In other words, the signal travels hidden and undercover for the distance segment shown in **Fig.2** inside the dark sector as instantaneous or possible superluminal speed and emerges out of the dark sector at the end of this segment as a normal muon pair due to dark sector oscillation kinetic mixing to our normal spacetime. See **Fig. 2**:

Figure 2 Temporal Displacement of observed signal's ToF due to initial hidden superluminal propagation in the dark sector distance segment. Base image used [1].

2. Conclusion

We demonstrated according to our previous related research [2-16] an important prediction concerning the hypothesized kinetic mixing with the dark sector of a Higgs Boson decay event into a muon pair although this could be also applied for γ -photons decay of the Higgs as previously described in our research [11]. That the signal travels initially and physically for a segment inside the detector hidden inside the dark sector at superluminal or instantaneous speed and emerges at the end of this distance segment as normal particles in our spacetime. Also, it is advised that the event filters of the detectors at CERN to be heavily updated and reprogrammed with new parameters to look for such anomalous ToF events during the new run of CERN by 2030, and unfortunately this important data of possible new physics were dismissed so far by the detectors.

References

- [1] PBS Channel, Most of Reality Is Invisible. We May Finally Be About to Reveal It. - YouTube. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=zaJrFVRe-Vg&t=966s> Accessed: 2026-03-09.
- [2] E.N. Markoulakis, Superluminal graviton condensate vacuum, *Int. J. Phys. Res.* 12 (2024) 45–61. doi:[10.14419/BMR9G725](https://doi.org/10.14419/BMR9G725). [hal-04663412v2](https://hal.archives-ouvertes.fr/hal-04663412v2)
- [3] E. Markoulakis, A. Valamontes, Experiment for the Detection of Superluminal Propagating Dark Photons at CERN and their Correlation with Gravitons and the Higgs Boson $H \rightarrow \gamma\gamma$ Decay Event, (2024). doi:[10.2139/SSRN.4950704](https://doi.org/10.2139/SSRN.4950704).
- [4] E. Markoulakis, Superluminal Dark Energy of Graviton Evaporating to Lorentz-Invariant Vacuum Zero-Point Energy, *SSRN Electron. J.* (2024). doi:[10.2139/SSRN.4789884](https://doi.org/10.2139/SSRN.4789884).
- [5] E.N. Markoulakis, W.D. Walker, E. Antonidakis, Nonlocal or Possibly Superluminal Maxwell Displacement Current Observed in the Near-Field of a Spherical Capacitor, *Int. J. Commun. Antenna Propag.* 14 (2024) 215. doi:[10.15866/irecap.v14i4.24903](https://doi.org/10.15866/irecap.v14i4.24903). [hal-04541585v2](https://hal.archives-ouvertes.fr/hal-04541585v2)
- [6] E.N. Markoulakis, The superluminous vacuum, *Int. J. Phys. Res.* 11 (2023) 18–25. doi:[10.14419/IJPR.V11I1.32269](https://doi.org/10.14419/IJPR.V11I1.32269). (SSRN -<https://ssrn.com/abstract=4602319>)
- [7] E. Markoulakis, The Big Flash: A Prediction of the Remaining Life Time of the Universe by Using an Intrinsic Superluminal Oscillating Vacuum Graviton Condensate, *SSRN Electron. J.* (2024). doi:[10.2139/SSRN.4789915](https://doi.org/10.2139/SSRN.4789915).
- [8] E. Markoulakis, Higgs Boson LHC detection by two γ -photons decay emission described as a superluminal Relativistic Image Doubling effect, *SSRN Electron. J.* (2024). doi:[10.2139/SSRN.4789892](https://doi.org/10.2139/SSRN.4789892).
- [9] E. Markoulakis, Calculation of an Upper Possible Size Limit for the Radius of the Graviton R_G , *SSRN Electron. J.* (2024). doi:[10.2139/SSRN.4789922](https://doi.org/10.2139/SSRN.4789922).
- [10] A. Valamontes, E.N. Markoulakis, I. Adamopoulos, Superluminal Dark Photons as a Solution to the GRB 221009A Anomaly, (2025). <https://arxiv.org/abs/2503.16253> (accessed March 25, 2025).
- [11] Emmanouil Markoulakis, Antonios Valamontes. Dark Photons and Their Correlation with The Dark Sector Gravitons and The Higgs Boson $H \rightarrow \gamma\gamma$ Decay. *International Journal of Physical Research* , 2025, 13 (2), pp.1 - 13. [10.14419/xhvxrg97](https://doi.org/10.14419/xhvxrg97). [hal-05204263v2](https://hal.archives-ouvertes.fr/hal-05204263v2)
- [12] Vasilaki, E.; Markoulakis, E.; Lazari, D.; Psaroudaki, A.; Barbounakis, I.; Antonidakis, E. A Novel Low-Frequency Electromagnetic Active Inertial Sensor for Drug Detection. *Sensors* **2024**, *24*, 3059. doi: [10.3390/s24103059](https://doi.org/10.3390/s24103059)
- [13] E.N. Markoulakis, Non Tachyonic Superluminal Graviton, https://www.researchgate.net/publication/373069613_Non_Tachyonic_Superluminal_Graviton (accessed August 27, 2023).
- [14] Emmanouil Markoulakis, Christian G. Wolf. New novel physical constants metric and fine structure constant models demonstrate the intrinsic nature of vacuum space as a quantum medium. *International Journal of Physical Research* , 2023, 11 (1), pp.15-17. [10.14419/ijpr.v11i1.32250](https://doi.org/10.14419/ijpr.v11i1.32250). [hal-05287009](https://hal.archives-ouvertes.fr/hal-05287009)

- [15] Emmanouil Markoulakis, Iraklis Rigakis, John Chatzakis, Antonios Konstantaras, Emmanuel Antonidakis, Real time visualization of dynamic magnetic fields with a nanomagnetic ferrolens, Journal of Magnetism and Magnetic Materials, Volume 451, 2018, Pages 741-748, ISSN 0304-8853, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmmm.2017.12.023>
- [16] E.N. Markoulakis, Estimation of the superluminal dark energy interaction propagation speed, https://www.researchgate.net/publication/372483116_Estimation_of_the_superluminal_dark_energy_interaction_propagation_speed (accessed August 11, 2023).

9 March 2026.